

THERMAL STABILITY OF PEEK COMPOSITES IN AIR: DYNAMIC RHEOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The thermal stability of PEEK-based composites is characterised under simulated processing conditions. The changes in dynamic shear modulus, glass transition temperature and crystallinity due to chemical reactions and morphology changes was monitored by dynamic rheological analysis and differential scanning calorimetry. The initial stage of the crosslinking reaction is modeled by an exponential expression. Significant differences in the dynamic shear modulus are observed between carbon fibre and glass fibre reinforced PEEK composites. Finally, a way of establishing a processing limit by dynamic rheological analysis is proposed.

Keywords: PEEK, thermal stability, dynamic rheological analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK) based composites are widely used in high performance composite applications. These composites are generally supplied as prepreg sheets with reinforcement of carbon fibres or glass fibres. The manufacturing step often involves significant exposure of the composite material to elevated temperatures, either directly in the mould or in an oven prior to moulding. The type of atmosphere and the duration of exposure to elevated temperature may drastically influence the thermal stability of the PEEK matrix and the interface between the matrix and reinforcing fibres. The morphology and physical properties of the material are changed during processing, depending on these conditions. The optimisation and control of the processing conditions are thus very important. Chain branching, crosslinking and decomposition have been proposed in order to describe the property change initiated by heat and oxygen exposure [1-6].

The aim of this work is to develop a simulation and characterisation technique for property changes occurring during conventional processing. This should serve as a tool for defining the processing window in terms of time and temperature for PEEK-based composites with defined fibre type and volume fraction.

The evaluation of the thermal stability of PEEK is carried out by dynamic rheological analysis and calorimetric analysis. The first part of the study covers rheological measurements showing the time evolution and temperature dependence of the rheological properties of the material. It is followed

by the development of an analytical model of the early stage of the crosslinking reaction, in order to define a limit to thermal exposure in terms of rheological properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

The PEEK-based composites used in this study were APC2/S2 and APC2/AS4 prepregs manufactured by ICI, with glass and carbon fibres, respectively.

2.2. Dynamic rheological analysis

The prepregs were subjected to a dynamic rheological analysis, using a torsional rheometer (Rheometrics RDA2-FRT) with $\phi 25$ mm parallel plates. Samples consisting of two 0° plies were tested isothermally in open air in the temperature range 370-420°C, during one hour. The strain amplitude was 2%.

2.3. Calorimetric analysis

The prepregs were tested by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, Perkin-Elmer system 7) in a nitrogen atmosphere. Samples identical to those used in the rheological analysis were heated up to 420°C in the oven of the rheometer, held at this temperature for different exposure times and then slowly cooled to room temperature. Samples containing between 5 and 10 mg of resin were then cut out and placed in open aluminium pans, and a temperature scan was performed at a rate of 20°C/min up to 400°C.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Dynamic rheological analysis

Figure 1 shows the time evolution of the dynamic shear modulus for APC2/AS4 at different temperatures in air. The initial difference in shear modulus is directly related to the temperature dependence of the resin viscosity. The slight decrease in shear modulus during the first ~100 seconds may be primarily due to local fibre and ply rearrangement. The subsequent increase in

Figure 1. Dynamic modulus G^* versus time for APC2/AS4 in air at 370, 380, 400 and 420°C.

shear modulus is related to permanent changes in the resin properties, attributed to crosslinking [1-3]. The dynamic modulus starts to change immediately even though the rate of change is low in the beginning. The rate of stiffening increases rapidly with temperature. The following levelling-off from the exponential behaviour (especially for the test at 420°C) may be attributed to the completion of the crosslinking reaction or, more probably, to extensive decomposition of the resin. Decomposition of the resin was verified by gravimetric analysis, which demonstrated a continuous weight reduction for samples exposed to oxygen.

3.2. Differential scanning calorimetry

Figures 2 and 3 show the evolution over time of the enthalpy of fusion, ΔH , and of the glass transition temperature, T_g , respectively, of the two types of prepreg. The scale of Figure 2 is normalised: ΔH is the enthalpy of fusion at time t and ΔH_0 is the initial enthalpy of fusion. The graph shows that the enthalpy of fusion decreases with time; this is indicative of decreasing crystallinity.

Figure 2. Enthalpy of fusion ΔH isothermally versus exposure time for the prepreps with glass (o) and carbon (◇) fibres exposed to air at 420°C.

Figure 3. Glass transition temperature T_g versus exposure time for the prepreps with glass (o) and carbon (◇) fibres exposed to air at 420°C.

Different authors have proposed that a rapid branching mechanism takes place in molten PEEK exposed to air, leading to crosslinking and consequently to a decreased crystallinity [4-6]. This is further confirmed by the increase of the glass transition temperature [4], see Figure 3. It can be concluded that crosslinking is the dominating mechanism occurring during the rheological measurements.

3.3. Analytical model

Figure 4 shows that the logarithm of the dynamic modulus ratio approximates a linear function of time during the initial stage. For temperatures equal to or lower than 380°C this holds for almost the full length of the measurement. The graph is normalised using the ratio G^*/G_o^* , where G_o^* is the lowest value of the dynamic modulus. For 400°C and 420°C, at longer times, a significant influence of the decomposition reaction is detectable. An expression describing the increase of viscosity in the initial stage of crosslinking was derived by Malkin et al. [8]:

$$\eta = \eta_o \cdot \exp(\theta t) \tag{1}$$

where η is the viscosity of the reactive system, η_o is the initial viscosity and θ is a constant. From the rheological relation $G^* = i\omega\eta^*$, where G^* and η^* are linearly related, Equation 1 leads to:

$$G^* = G_o^* \cdot \exp(k' t) \tag{2}$$

where G_o^* is the initial complex modulus. The constant k' is calculated by linear regression over the linear domain of the plot of $\ln(G^*/G_o^*)$ versus t , and the results are listed in Table 1. The linear relationship between k' and $1/T$, as evidenced in Figure 5, suggests that k' follows an Arrhenius type equation:

$$k' = k_o' \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \tag{3}$$

where k_o' is a constant, E_a is the activation energy and R is the universal gas constant. Introducing

Figure 4. The value of $\ln(G^*/G_o^*)$ versus time for carbon fibre-reinforced PEEK composite.

Table 1. The value of k' as a function of temperature.

Temperature (°C)	k' (10^{-4} s^{-1})	
	APC2/S2	APC2/AS4
370	2.99	3.85
380	-	5.72
400	7.22	9.57
420	11.26	20.5

Figure 5. Plot of $\ln(k')$ versus $1/T$ for APC2/AS4 and APC2/S2.

Equation 3 into Equation 2 allows the initial stage of the reaction to be described as:

$$G^* = G_o^* \cdot \exp\left\{\left[k'_o \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right)\right]t\right\} \quad (4)$$

The calculated values of the activation energy E_a and the constant k'_o are listed in Table 2. The prediction of the normalised dynamic shear modulus versus time and temperature is plotted in Figure 6. Equation 2 is an exponential function with a constant k' which is temperature dependent. This empirical relation gives a good approximation to the evolution of modulus over a certain time range for different temperatures.

Table 2. Values of the activation energy E_a , the constant k'_o .

Material	Activation energy (kJ/mol)	k'_o (10^4 s^{-1})
APC2/AS4	120.17±7.94	223.5
APC2/S2	98.97±5.3	3.33

The values of E_a and k'_o are different for APC2/AS4 and APC2/S2. This could, on one hand, be due to the different surface chemistry of the glass and carbon fibers [3] and, on the other hand, to

Figure 6. Plot of the experimental and calculated (Equation 4) ratio G^*/G_o^* versus time and temperature for APC2/AS4 and APC2/S2.

the difference of total interface area between resin and fibres, which is roughly twice as large for APC2/AS4 as for APC2/S2, for the same fibre volume content.

The limit for thermal exposure can be expressed in terms of the dynamic modulus ratio. In section 3.2, it was shown that the increase of the shear modulus is related to the evolution of crosslinking. One can define a limiting value of the dynamic modulus ratio, below which the increase of stiffness still allows a good processability. In this study, for example, the limiting value of the dynamic modulus ratio is chosen to be 2. As can be seen in Table 3, this corresponds to different times of exposure at various test temperatures.

A discrepancy between the prediction and the experimental data is observed at long times or high temperatures, where thermal decomposition occurs simultaneously with the crosslinking reaction. The model does not account for such a mechanism, which starts well above the processability limits defined in this work.

Table 3. Limits of thermal exposure for APC2/AS4 and APC2/S2 for a dynamic modulus ratio $G^*/G_o^*=2$.

Temperature (°C)	time of exposure (s)	
	APC2/S2	APC2/AS4
370	2500	1900
380	-	1140
400	950	680
420	600	360

4. CONCLUSION

The crosslinking of PEEK resin in a composite is a reaction which occurs in the presence of oxygen at temperatures commonly used for processing. The resin begins to crosslink without induction time, but with a clear temperature dependence. The rheological properties of the changes in the resin due to thermal exposure can be monitored by measuring the dynamic shear modulus.

The shear modulus ratio, as it is related to the crosslinking, is suggested as a measure of processability.

The change in the dynamic modulus ratio due to crosslinking of PEEK was modelled by an exponential relation. The time range of validity of this model covers the range of interest for manufacturing.

Significant different values of the activation energy for the crosslinking reaction are obtained for APC2/AS4 and APC2/S2.

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